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Powering options for an EIC silicon tracker

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Introduction

Powering an EIC tracker presents several critical aspects. In particular, the extremely low material budget profile combined with the requirement for the detector to be almost hermetic ($|\eta| < \sim 3.5$) makes it challenging to accommodate the required services and it calls for powering options that move past state-of-the-art developments to further reduce material budget contributions due to cables, power buses and active circuitry, while not compromising electrical stability and safety of the detector. In addition, the EIC tracker power system will have to operate in a moderate dose radiation environment and under an up to 3T magnetic field which pose a limit to the number of commercially available parts that can be used to implement active powering circuitry. After a brief description of the EIC silicon tracker and power system requirements, this document provides a detailed overview of the powering options that could be prototyped and studied for possible use in the EIC tracker. All the proposed powering schemes are variations of the ALICE ITS-2 detector powering scheme with modifications introduced to improve material budget and overall detector performance and using as reference the expected current profiles and voltage envelopes for the ITS-3 sensor under development.

The EIC silicon tracker

The EIC silicon tracker is envisioned as an all-silicon pixel detector with a total surface coverage of 12-15m². The detector consists of a 6-layer central barrel and a set of 10 disks, 5 in the forward and 5 in the backward pseudorapidity regions. The 2 innermost layers in the central barrel employ air cooling while the 4 outermost layers employ liquid cooling. The disks employ liquid cooling.

The geometrical parameters and radiation hardness requirements for the staves in the central barrel are listed in the following table:

Object	Parameter	Value/Requirement
Layer 1 staves (~7 modules)	Material budget	0.1%
	Length [mm]	300
	Width [mm]	30
	Min distance from IP [mm]	33
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n _{eq} cm ⁻²]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm ⁻²]	TBD
Layer 2 staves (~12 modules)	Material budget	0.1%
	Length [mm]	300
	Width [mm]	30
	Min distance from IP [mm]	57
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n _{eq} cm ⁻²]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm ⁻²]	TBD
Layer 3 staves (~80 modules)	Material budget	0.55%
	Length [mm]	540
	Width [mm]	30
	Min distance from IP [mm]	210
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n _{eq} cm ⁻²]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm ⁻²]	TBD
Layer 4 staves (~95 modules)	Material budget	0.55%

	Length [mm]	600
	Width [mm]	30
	Min distance from IP [mm]	226.8
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n_{eq} cm^{-2}]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm^{-2}]	TBD
Layer 5 staves (~288 modules)	Material budget	0.55%
	Length [mm]	1050
	Width [mm]	30
	Min distance from IP [mm]	393
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n_{eq} cm^{-2}]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm^{-2}]	TBD
Layer 6 staves (~344 modules)	Material budget	0.55%
	Length [mm]	1140
	Width [mm]	30
	Min distance from IP [mm]	432.3
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n_{eq} cm^{-2}]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm^{-2}]	TBD

The geometrical parameters and radiation hardness requirements for the disks (only 5, other 5 are identical and positioned symmetrically wrt IP) are listed in the following table:

Object	Parameter	Value/Requirement
Disk 1	Material budget	0.24%
	Radius inner/outer [mm]	31.8/185
	Min distance from IP [mm]	250
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n_{eq} cm^{-2}]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm^{-2}]	TBD
Disk 2	Material budget	0.24%
	Radius inner/outer [mm]	31.8/362.6
	Min distance from IP [mm]	490
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n_{eq} cm^{-2}]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm^{-2}]	TBD
Disk 3	Material budget	0.24%
	Radius inner/outer [mm]	35/432.3
	Min distance from IP [mm]	730
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n_{eq} cm^{-2}]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm^{-2}]	TBD
Disk 4	Material budget	0.24%
	Radius inner/outer [mm]	47/432.3
	Min distance from IP [mm]	970
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n_{eq} cm^{-2}]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm^{-2}]	TBD
Disk 5	Material budget	0.24%
	Radius inner/outer [mm]	59.1/432.3
	Min distance from IP [mm]	1210
	TID [krad], center and side	TBD
	NIEL [1 MeV n_{eq} cm^{-2}]	TBD
	High LET fluence [cm^{-2}]	TBD

In the following sections the detector is assumed to be built using 30mm x 300mm modules (about 830 in the central barrel and about 500 in the disks) of ITS-3-like sensors designed in the TowerJazz 65nm process (input voltage 1.2V). Each module is made of one or multiple sensors depending on layer, disk number and sensor yield in the TJ 65nm CMOS process (unknown at the moment). Radiation hardness requirements for the EIC tracker sensors are unknown but expected to be less stringent than the radiation hardness requirements for the ALPIDE sensors used in the ALICE ITS-2. The current consumption figures for the EIC tracker modules are assumed to be about 0.5A digital (dynamic current consumption in ITS-3 modules assumed to be 50% of ITS-2 modules because of process voltage decrease by 33% from 1.8V to 1.2V, lower gate capacitance and architectural improvements) and 0.2A analog (static current consumption for ITS-3 modules same as for ITS-2 modules). The outermost layers of the detector are assumed to be 4-module long (1 module length being about 300mm) in the z direction; the innermost layers are assumed to be 2-module long; the middle layer structures are assumed to be either 2 or 3 module long; no assumption is made on the structure of the disks. No in-depth considerations on bias generation and distribution are included in this document at the moment. Bias is assumed to be delivered to the detector structures on a stave or half-stave basis in a similar fashion as to what done for ALICE ITS-2.

Power system requirements

The main constraints for the power systems are the following (work in progress):

- 1) Space/Geometrical
 - a) Based on detector geometry as described in the previous section and available space in the experiment
- 2) Radiation hardness
 - a) TID: to define
 - b) NIEL: to define
 - c) High LET particles fluence: to define
- 3) Material budget
 - a) Based on detector material budget requirements in the previous section and other requirements for material budget outside the detector volume (to be defined)
- 4) Grounding
 - a) To define: Stave-wise or module-wise grounding in central barrel
 - b) To define: Stave-wise or module-wise grounding in disks
- 5) Operational/granularity
 - a) Ability to interface to an external power/control/interlock system
 - b) Allow for the readout of voltages/currents/temperatures
 - c) Overvoltage/overcurrent/overtemperature protection mechanisms
 - d) Implement redundancy to mitigate single point failure issues
- 6) Electrical
 - a) The power system must be able to keep voltage sufficiently stable at the sensors in all foreseen current conditions (within +/-10% of 1.2V)

DC-DC converters

Step-down switching DC-DC converters offer the advantage of efficient voltage conversion and enable the possibility to deliver power at high voltage (~tens of V), leading to a significant reduction of the mass of the cables connecting the off-detector electronics to the detector with respect to other architectures based on linear regulators. To benefit the most from the use of DC-DC converters and keep material budget as low as possible, the last stage of voltage conversion should be placed as close as possible to the sensors. Integration of this last stage of voltage conversion in the sensors would offer maximal benefit but it would require, in the current technological state, extensive R&D to explore the feasibility of such configuration and fully characterize its electrical performance. Several powering options suitable for an EIC tracker and based on switching DC-DC converters are described below.

Fixed voltage DC-DC converters outside the detector volume

Commercially available fixed-voltage DC-DC converters

Commercial-Off-The-Shelf (COTS) DC-DC converters can be a suitable option for use in the EIC tracker provided that their resilience to the radiation load at their location can be proven along with their reliable operation in the EIC magnetic field. While testing for radiation tolerance and in a magnetic field can be cumbersome, some options of fixed-voltage radiation-hardened DC-DC converters that can be operated in a magnetic field are either readily available or under prototyping. One of these is the CERN FEASTMP DC-DC converter (fig. 1 Left, fig. 2) which can generate voltages in the range 0.9-5V (fixed at purchase, current strength up to 4A) from up to 12V input voltage and withstand 200 Mrad TID while working in magnetic fields in excess of 4T. In addition, the CERN microelectronics team is currently working on new DC-DC converter prototypes based on radiation hard design for future CERN experiments that can be powered at up to 60V and provide output voltages down to 1.2V at up to 12A currents (fig. 1 Right).

Fig 1. Left: CERN FESTMP DC-DC converter (low profile version) [1,2]. Right: Prototype of a CERN buck converter with commercial GaN power device and Rad-Hard ASIC controller [3].

The CERN DC-DC converters will require cooling to remove the heat generated due to voltage conversion inefficiencies. From the FEASTMP DC-DC converter datasheet and assuming that up to 4 modules with 0.85A max current* each can be connected to a converter, the expected efficiency for an output voltage of 1.2V and an input voltage of 12V is above 60% (for currents up to 4A, fig. 4), or roughly 66% of the power dissipated in the sensors would be dissipated in the DC-DC converters. Therefore, each FEASTMP DC-DC converter is expected to dissipate less than 0.7W per module connected to it (takes into account current margins) or 2.8W in the 4 module per DC-DC converter configuration. In configurations in which the DC-DC converters draw a lower current, the power dissipated per module in the DC-DC converters would be lower by virtue of the higher DC-DC converter efficiency at lower currents, therefore the value of 0.7W per module for the dissipated power in the DC-DC converters should be considered as an absolute maximum, provided that the module current figures used as reference are correct.

* assuming 0.5A digital current + 0.2A analog current per module + 0.15A pessimism or margin.

Figure 2 [2]. Top: efficiency plots (Left: efficiency vs current load, Right: efficiency vs TID @ Iout = 2A and Vout = 2.5V). Center: Voltage regulation plots (Left: Vout vs Vin, Right: Vout vs Iout). Bottom: Noise plots (Left: residual switching ripple @2A, Right: voltage regulation at current steps 0A → 2A and 2A → 0A).

Possible locations for the DC-DC converters

The CERN DC-DC converters are unlikely to be placed inside the detector volume because of their high contribution to material budget. The locations that appear to be the most appropriate for the placement of the DC-DC converters are next to the sides of the outermost layers staves and/or around the beam pipe, next to the outermost disks. Sense wires may or may not be necessary to keep the voltages at the input of the DC-DC converters stable. The voltages generated by the DC-DC converters would be delivered to the detector via Flexible Printed Circuits (FPC) made of Kapton and Aluminum (see section on FPC cables) routed through the gap between the central barrel and the disks and, if needed, around the beam pipe.

Figure 3: possible locations for the DC-DC converter circuitry

Implementation of the DC-DC converter circuit

The DC-DC converters would be loaded on PCBs mechanically integrated in the detector support structures in a manner that will depend on the available space/material budget requirements. The output voltages on the DC-DC converters would be adjusted by replacing

onboard resistors to compensate known DC drops across the power paths downstream the DC-DC converters to the detector structures. In order to read the DC-DC converter currents back into the off-detector electronics, additional components may be required on the DC-DC converter PCBs. A simple baseline configuration for this circuitry would include, aside from the converter and interface connectors, a shunt resistor and an amplifier circuit to deliver current signals with a sufficiently high S/N back to the off-detector electronics. This may be necessary to detect latch-up conditions and power cycle the affected areas of the detector during to prevent or limit damage induced by radiation. The radiation hardness of the amplifier circuit would need to be assessed or radiation hardened technologies by design would have to be purchased. Each PCB Unit (DC-DC converter + amplifier circuit) would therefore have the following connections:

- Two input power connections (12V power + return, may be shared with other units)
- Two sense connections for the input power (may or may not be needed)
- One enable signal (may not be needed depending on configuration)
- Two output connections to the detector (1.2V power + return)
- Four output connections to the off-detector electronics
 - DC-DC converter output
 - Local ground (may be shared with other units)
 - Differential amplified current signal (more than one may be needed depending on configuration)

Off-detector electronics/DC-DC converter connection topologies

Various power connection topologies can be implemented in the EIC tracker. All suitable options are described in the following sections in decreasing order of granularity of the power connections. The following discussion does not include considerations related to the granularity of monitoring signals and bias. For the sake of simplicity, all the calculations assume that each positive voltage output channel in the off-detector electronics generates a fixed voltage of 12V (no sense, 11V at the input of the DC-DC converters @0.85A per module) and that the DC-DC converters efficiency is 60% regardless of current conditions.

Point-to-point power connection topology (conf 1)

In this configuration each supply channel in the off-detector electronics powers a DC-DC converter (or pair of converters if the module analog and digital domains are powered from the same source) via an independent set of up to four connections (two power + two optional sense connections) and no enable connection (tied to input power). This provides the finest control over the detector and least amount of noise as each off-detector channel powers a minimum number of modules. Assuming 10m-long wires connecting off-detector electronics and DC-DC converters and 1V drop across those wires, AWG30 could be used to power a single module (both digital and analog) from the same converter and AWG24 could be used to power four modules (both digital and analog).

Figure 4: Point to point configuration: each off-detector channel connects to one or two DC-DC converters depending on domain powering configuration (common or split).

Point-to-multipoint power/point-to-point enable connection topology (conf 2)

In this configuration each supply channel in the off-detector electronics powers in parallel a set of DC-DC converters via a set of up to four connections (two power + two optional sense connections). A number of enable signals equal to the number of powered DC-DC converters (half of it in case DC-DC converters are controlled in pairs to power digital and analog separately) are also used. Assuming 10m-long wires connecting off-detector electronics and DC-DC converters and 1V drop across the wires, up to about 100 DC-DC converters (each powering digital and analog domain of a module) can be connected to the same 12V/9A off-detector channel using AWG10 wire for power + return, or up to 25 DC-DC converters (each powering 4 entire modules). AWG30 wire could be used to carry the enable signals to the DC-DC converters.

Figure 5: point to multipoint power configuration: each off-detector electronics powers a set DC-DC converters each powering both the digital and analog domain of a set of detector modules

Figure 6: point to multipoint power configuration: each off-detector electronics powers a set DC-DC converters each powering either the digital or the analog domain of a set of detector modules

DC-DC converter/module connection topologies

Flexible Printed Circuits as interconnects

At the moment, the only available option to interconnect DC-DC converters outside the detector volume and modules in the detector volume would be Flexible Printed Circuits. A baseline

stackup for the FPCs could be based on 5 layers (2 x 50um-thick coverlay layers + 2 x 100um-thick Aluminum layers + 1 x 50um-thick inner Kapton layer between the aluminum layers). One Aluminum layer would carry power/bias and the other one would be used to implement the return traces. Based on the current conceptual design for the EIC tracker, 4 power FPC traces and up to 4 FPC return traces would be necessary to power the longest independent detector structures (half outer layer staves, this does not account for bias and bias return traces). Trace resistances (per unit current) could be equalized to avoid having to use a different set of resistors to set voltages on the DC-DC converters for different module positions along the detector structures as was done in the ALICE ITS-2 implementation. In the following sections, several connection topologies for the modules in the outermost layers of the EIC tracker (the outermost staves are assumed to be segmented power-wise into is 2-module long structures, and to have a total length of 4 modules) are presented, where it is assumed that the minimum clearance between each pair of traces is 200um as well as the minimum trace width (current manufacturing capabilities for Aluminum FPCs with 100 um thick conductor). It is assumed that each module has its own bias connection to the off-detector electronics, routed on top of a dedicated common (with the other bias traces) return trace. If the total width of the FPC is 30mm, on the top metal layer about 4mm could be used to route the bias traces (500um per bias trace) and 26mm could be used to route the power traces (an equal amount of metal width would be available to route the return trace(s) on the bottom layer).

FPC grounding by domain

In this configuration two modules are powered via 4 power plus 4 return traces to minimize noise in the analog domains. In order to achieve equalized analog and digital voltage drops, the resistance of the digital power/return traces is 2.5 times lower than that of the analog traces (since nominal operating currents are 0.5A digital and 0.2A analog). Assuming that an FPC is as long as 60cm (3 cm longer than the longest independent detector structure) and that all power domains of the two modules are connected to the midpoint of the FPC for simplicity, the resistance of each digital trace and analog trace would be 8.6mOhm and 21.5mOhm respectively. With the modules operating at nominal currents, the drops on the digital or analog path (power + return) would be below 12mV. Therefore analog and digital grounds on each module would sit within +/-12mV of each other in all current conditions.

Figure 7: Fully split ground configuration for the FPC

FPC grounding by module

In this configuration digital and analog grounds are shorted to prevent build-up of voltage offsets between analog and digital domains in the same module. This may be necessary if the thickness or width of the traces is significantly reduced to reduce the material budget of the FPC.

Figure 8: FPC: common ground configuration (on a module basis)

DC-DC converter powering by domain

The grounding configurations proposed in the previous sections allow for various connection topologies between DC-DC converters and modules. A split analog/digital ground configuration allows powering analog and digital domains separately, thereby minimizing coupling of the digital noise into the analog domain. This configuration uses two FEASTMP DC-DC converters to power up to 6 modules. The analog power traces are shorted together at the corresponding DC-DC converter unit as well as the analog return traces. The same considerations apply for the digital traces. Analog and digital grounds are made common at the DC-DC converter unit area. Each DC-DC converter is therefore capable of powering in parallel up to 6 either digital or analog power domains.

Figure 9: Dedicated DC-DC converters powering either the digital or analog domain of a set of modules (up to 6)

DC-DC converter powering by module

In the case digital noise conductively coupled into the analog domain is not an issue, either of the two FPC types can be used. Each module is entirely powered using the same DC-DC converter which allows minimizing the total number of DC-DC converters required to power the full detector. In this configuration all module common ground traces are shorted at the DC-DC converter unit. Similar considerations apply to the digital power traces and to the analog power traces. Each DC-DC converter is therefore powering in parallel a set of up to 4 modules.

Figure 10: DC-DC converters each powering both the digital and analog domain of a set of modules (up to 4)

DC-DC converters in the detector volume

Configuration and limitations

In order to further decrease DC-DC converter board and cable weight outside the detector volume and material budget of the FPCs in the detector volume, other powering configurations would need to be explored. One of these consists in integrating DC-DC converter circuits directly in the sensors. This would provide the following advantages over using DC-DC converters outside the detector volume:

- The possibility to fully eliminate all PCBs and circuitry near the detector volume
- The possibility to reduce cable mass by designing the integrated DC-DC converters to operate at higher voltages than the CERN DC-DC converters
- The possibility to further reduce the material budget of the FPCs that deliver power to the modules
- The certainty that adjustable voltages would not be needed

However this configuration presents some disadvantages:

- Hard to implement. It would require an extensive R&D effort and involve multiple institutions, possibly CERN that has significant experience with the design of radiation hard DC-DC converters that can work in magnetic fields.
- It would require additional passive components in the detector volume (possibly loaded on FPCs).
- It would require assessing the effects of the integration of a switching component to the performance of a sensitive device (pixel sensor).

Types of DC-DC converters that could be studied

To be done (if necessary)

Summary on DC-DC converter configurations

Although developing a powering scheme based on DC-DC converters integrated in the sensors would allow for a significant reduction of material budget in and near the detector volume, this is at the moment an entirely unexplored option. On the contrary, a solution based on fixed voltage DC-DC converters is implementable and should therefore become the baseline powering scheme for an EIC silicon tracker.

By using fixed voltage DC-DC converters on the detector sides, material budget due to cabling outside the detector volume can be significantly reduced compared to previous developments (such as ALICE ITS-2) due to the expected lower current profile of the EIC detector modules and the possibility to deliver higher voltages (1.8V \rightarrow 11V) to the sides of the detector. It is estimated that this would lead to an improvement of at least a factor 16 in the mass of digital/analog/return wires (not considering wire insulation). This improvement would come at the cost of having to install a set of DC-DC converters printed circuit boards as well as other auxiliary circuitry on the two sides of the detector to step down voltages from 11V to 1.2V and amplify current signals. The number of DC-DC converters that are necessary to power the central barrel is between about 210 and 1700 depending on the chosen granularity and whether analog and digital domains are powered independently. The disks would require between 125 and 1000 DC-DC converters, which gives a total number of FEASTMP DC-DC converters between about 335 (0.25m² total DC-DC converter PCB surface or 0.125m² PCB surface per detector side) and 2700 (2m² total DC-DC converter PCB surface or 1m² PCB surface per detector side). In addition to this, it will be necessary to install a number of current sense circuits equal to the total number of detector channels. Assuming a PCB area of 1cm² to design this circuit and that another 1cm² is necessary for the placement of interface connectors, this would bring the total instrumented area (PCB area) on the sides of the detector to between 1.25m² and 3m² (or half of these values per detector side).

Concerning the various configurations proposed in the fixed voltage DC-DC converter section:

- Off-detector electronics to DC-DC converter interface: as stated above, both solutions enable a significant reduction in terms of material budget with respect to state-of-the-art developments. None of the two solutions is preferred in this respect, as, in order to keep the voltage drops across the cables below 1V, the same total cross sectional area of metal is required for a given cable length for both solutions. Specific choices of wire type and more refined calculations that include wire insulation might lead to a slightly different conclusion, however the two solutions can be considered equivalent at the moment in terms of total material budget due to cables outside the EIC tracker volume, the only exception being the distribution of the cable mass (more flat in configuration 1 and concentrated in configuration 2). The main difference between the two configurations is modularity. Configuration 1 is more modular than configuration 2, however configuration 2 would allow simplifying the off-detector power system by splitting it into a high-current section with almost no functionality and a few channels (a few tens of channels at the most, perhaps purchasable off the shelf) from a custom multi-channel (up to a few thousand channels) voltage/current readout and control section that would be implemented on separate boards.

- DC-DC converter to module interface: among the various configurations proposed, the one with split ground FPCs and “specialized” DC-DC converters that either power the analog or digital domain of a set of modules appears to be the highest performing in terms of analog noise. On the other hand, using FPCs based on common ground at a module level would enable employing lower material budget FPCs. It was estimated that, in nominal current conditions and assuming 100um-thick traces, the total voltage drop across the FPC traces down to a module would be lower than 12mV. This opens the possibility to use 25um-thick metal layers in the FPCs and possibly integrate both power and high speed signals in the same, leading to a significant reduction in material budget with respect to the outer layers of the ALICE ITS-2 detector. It needs to be determined whether a split ground configuration for the FPC with 25um thick traces could be safely used, as it would lead to digital-analog ground offsets in the range +/-50mV that may not be tolerated by the technology. Concerning granularity, i.e. how many modules can be connected to each DC-DC converter, this has to be determined based on material budget constraints outside the detector volume and requirements on the operation of the detector, particularly with respect to latch-up and other single event effects that may require parts of the detector to be periodically power cycled.

Serial powering

Serial powering is currently employed in the ATLAS inner tracker and it is the baseline powering scheme for ATLAS and CMS at the HL-LHC (the development of a serial powering scheme/circuit is part of the RD53 project whose goal is to develop sensors for the two experiments at the HL-LHC). When compared to configurations that use DC-DC converters outside the detector volume, serial powering offers the advantage of a reduced number of FPC traces with reduced cross sectional dimensions and it allows scaling the system without affecting material budget. In addition, the sides of the detector do not need to be instrumented.

Principle of operation

In the configurations described above (DC-DC converters outside the detector volume), each module/group of modules is powered independently via a set of DC-DC converters located in close proximity to the detector. This requires a large number of traces to be implemented on FPC, and it requires instrumenting the sides of the detector, which both negatively affect material budget. Serial powering overcomes this limitation by daisy-chaining modules and powering them using only two FPC traces per input voltage.

In the basic configuration a group of modules are connected in series, i.e. an input (power) node receives power via the output (ground) connection of the previous module in the chain. A current source is used to force a constant current through the chain of sensors. A set of Shunt LDO regulators (SLDO) on each module are designed to maintain stable analog and digital voltages at the input of the sensor circuitry. In order to achieve voltage stability in constant current mode, the two SLDO have to drain to the next module in the chain the excess current, i.e. the difference between the current imposed by the current source and the current used by

the module. In this way a chain of N modules can be powered using a single set of lines and at voltage $N * V$, where V is the voltage drop at any of the modules in the chain.

Figure 11: Serial powering: a chain of modules is powered using a single set of power lines and a current source

The magnitude of the current imposed by the current source has to exceed the total current needed for a proper operation in each module (i.e. headroom always has to be positive). Some decoupling is required inside and near each module to absorb high-amplitude short time constant current peaks, which may not be compensated by the SLDO. In addition, optimizing this decoupling circuitry allows reducing the magnitude of the imposed currents, i.e the detector power density.

Figure 12: Digital/analog module current profiles and SLDO current absorption in a serially powered detector module [4]

Connection topologies

The basic scheme presented in the previous section is a fully serial powering scheme. While it allows powering the detector using the lowest possible current and it is therefore highly beneficial to material budget, it does not protect against single point of failure issues that can take down a large portion of the system (e.g. a stove). The following sections describe some configurations that are used in the real case that provide some level of protection against such types of issues. Which of the following configurations should be developed for an EIC tracker cannot be determined at the moment and it is dependent on several factors, including the dimensions of the EIC sensors (dependent on sensor yield in the selected CMOS process).

Across-module serial powering

In this configuration, modules are connected in series and to an external current source. Inside each module, all sensors are connected in parallel. In case of failure of an SLDO, the constant current will be split among the SLDOs that are still functional in the same module. Since this will cause the power density in those SLDOs to increase, the SLDOs have to be designed to handle the power increase due to failure of multiple sensors in a chain for a given chain current.

Figure 13: Serial powering: across-module configuration [4]. Modules are connected in series (right), but sensors inside each module are connected in parallel and share the imposed current (left). A chain of modules will still work if one or more (but not all) sensors fail on one or more serially powered modules.

In-module serial powering

In this configuration, each module is independently powered by a current source. Inside each module, sensors are powered serially as in a fully serial powering scheme. In this case, the failure of a sensor will compromise one module but not an entire stave, unless the two coincide.

Figure 14: Serial powering: in-module configuration [4]. Modules are connected in parallel via independent links and sensors inside each module are connected in series. The failure of one sensor in one module will only compromise a single module.

Summary on serial powering

Serial powering allows reducing the number of power connections between the off-detector electronics and the detector which leads to a significantly improved material budget profile both outside and inside the detector volume as compared to ALICE ITS-2 figures.

An across-module serial powering scheme is preferable for an EIC tracker if the number of sensors per module is low (<4). This scheme could be used to power 4 modules in series (an outer layer stave, or two middle layer staves in series). Powering more than 4 modules in series may also be possible, depending on requirements on granularity, but it would require daisy chaining multiple staves. Powering less than 4 modules in series may be necessary in the inner layers or in the disks.

Assuming a 4-module configuration for serial powering, and that less than 5% of the power required to operate the sensors is dissipated in the cables and less than 5% of the same power is dissipated in the FPC, this would lead to the following choices for cables and FPC design:

- Cables:
 - 2 x 10m-long AWG20 wires to power 4 modules in series (analog + digital)
- FPC:
 - 2 x 100cm-long 7mm-wide 25 μ m-thick traces to power 4 modules in series (analog + digital)

Conclusions

Two main powering schemes for an EIC silicon tracker were described in this document: the first (DC-DC converter powering scheme) is based on the use of step down DC-DC converters on

the sides of the detector and the second one (serial powering) is based on the use of shunt LDO regulators implemented in silicon to connect modules and/or sensors within them in series and consequently reduce the number and cross sectional area of the FPC traces in the detector volume. A summary of the expected improvement in material budget or related quantities that would be achievable in the outer layers of an EIC silicon tracker with the two schemes as compared to the ALICE ITS-2 outer layers powering scheme is shown in the table below for the following configurations:

Fixed voltage DC-DC converter configurations:

- Each DC-DC converter powers in parallel up to 4 modules (up to 2 modules per stave).
- Wire configurations:
 - 2 x AWG30 wires outside the detector volume (single module powering)
 - 2 x AWG24 wires outside the detector volume (4 module powering)
- FPC configuration:
 - 8 x 25um-thick equalized voltage drops traces

Serial powering configurations:

- Each current source in the off-detector electronics powers in series up to 4 modules
- Wire configurations:
 - 2 x AWG20 wires outside the detector volume per 4 modules
 - 2 x AWG20 wires outside the detector volume per module
- FPC configuration:
 - 2 x 100cm-long 7mm-wide 25um-thick traces on the FPC

	Material budget (as a percentage of reference: ALICE ITS-2)			Development time (prototyping and characterization)
	Analog/digital/ground cable mass (outside detector volume)	PCB surface (detector sides)	FPC power bus material budget (inside detector volume)	
ALICE ITS-2 architecture (ITS-3 sensor modules)*	~50%	~100%	~66%	~1.5 years
DC-DC converters	3.125% - 6.25%	87% - 208%	~40%	~1.5 years
Serial powering	8% - 32%	5% - 20%	30 - 40%	~5 years

*Architecture based on off-detector power board with linear regulators and cable sections and FPC traces rescaled to take into account the lower magnitudes of digital currents expected for ITS-3 sensor modules as compared to ITS-2 modules

The DC-DC converter configuration allows for the highest reduction in the mass of the cables, however it comes at the cost of an increased amount of PCB material on the sides of the detector. In the detector volume, due to both reduced module currents and the possibility to power the detector from both sides thereby reducing the length of the FPCs, material budget is significantly improved. This solution is relatively simple to prototype and characterize, as most components of the system are either already available or easily manufacturable.

The serial powering configuration provides the advantage of reduced PCB material on the sides of the detector as well as reduced cable weight as compared to ALICE ITS-2. In the detector volume, it is estimated that the material budget of the FPCs would be reduced to 30% of the ALICE ITS-2 value. The development time for this solution is however much longer as it includes several prototyping runs for the shunt regulator as well as a thorough characterization of a chain of multiple modules to assess stability and reliability of this configuration.

References

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https://espace.cern.ch/project-DCDC-new/_layouts/15/start.aspx#/RandD/Research%20and%20development.aspx

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